

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The present study was conducted to investigate emotional intelligence of higher secondary students in relation to certain demographic variables viz. gender, locality of school, type of management, religion, caste, parental qualification and parental occupation. Emotional intelligence is defined as one of the important aspects in educating a person to be balanced as a whole. Through emotional intelligence, one will become more successful in life as compared to individuals that gain solely high levels of intellectual intelligence (IQ). Emotional intelligence also provides liberty for individuals to explore self potentials, as well as providing opportunities for individuals to harmonize themselves with their self emotion. Differential method of research was used for collecting the data using Emotional intelligence by Scale Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Detha and Upinder Dhar (2001). Sample included 240 randomly selected higher secondary students from various schools at Vellore City. Inferential statistics were used to compare the means between the groups. Findings of the study revealed that (1) there is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to their gender, locality of school, type of management, religion, caste, parental qualification and parental occupation.

Keys Words: Emotional Intelligence & Higher Secondary Students

Introduction:

Emotional Intelligence is the type of Social Intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and other's emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use the information to guide one's thinking and actions.

Perceiving Emotions:

The first step in understanding emotions is to accurately perceive them. In many cases, this might involve understanding nonverbal signals such as body language and facial expressions.

Reasoning with Emotions:

The next step involves using emotions to promote thinking and cognitive activity. Emotions help prioritize what we pay attention and react to; we respond emotionally to things that garner our attention.

Understanding Emotions:

The emotions that we perceive can carry a wide variety of meanings. If someone is expressing angry emotions, the observer must interpret the cause of their anger and what it might mean. For example, if your boss is acting angry, it might mean that he is dissatisfied with your work; or it could be because he got a speeding ticket on his way to work that morning or that he's been fighting with his wife.

Managing Emotions:

The ability to manage emotions effectively is a key part of emotional intelligence. Regulating emotions, responding appropriately and responding to the emotions of others are all important aspects of emotional management. Peter Salovey and John Mayer two psychologists from Yale University coined the phrase emotional intelligence in 1990 in the journal „Imagination, cognition and Personality. However, the concept of emotional intelligence gained popularity through Goleman's (1995) best seller titled Emotional Intelligence. He defined emotional intelligence in 1998 as Emotional Intelligence refers to the capacity of recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in our selves our relationships.

Need and Significance of the Study:

All human beings have basic emotional intelligence. This intelligence can be expressed as feelings, for example the need to feel accepted, respected and important while all humans share these needs, each differ in the strength of need, just as some of us need more water, more food, more sleep. One person may need more freedom and independence; another may need more security and social connections. Knowing about one's Emotional Intelligence in terms of an Emotion Quotient has wide educational and social implications for the welfare of the individual and the society. This fact has now been recognized and given practical shape and implication all around the globe. The credit of giving due publicity and acquainting the world-wide population about the importance of books like EI why it can matter more than IQ and working with Emotional Intelligence. A person's Emotional Intelligence helps him much in all spheres of life through its various constituents or

components the achievement of the end results in terms of better handling of mutual relationships is quite essential and significant in his life. It can only be possible through his potential of Emotional Intelligence and its proper development.

Aim of the Study:

The study was aimed on the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.

Sample:

The sample of the study was the higher secondary students from different schools in Vellore district, Tamilnadu. The sample was restricted to 240 higher secondary students to the investigator for the study. Government, private and aided is considered for the investigation.

Tool:

Emotional Intelligence Scale Standardized by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Dethe and Upinder Dhar (2001), Vedant Publications, Lucknow.

Methodology:

The present investigation is meant to study the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students from Vellore district. Normative survey method was adopted for the conduct of the present study. The sample consisted of 240 higher secondary students randomly selected from vellore district in Tamilnadu. In order to collect data for the study the tool which was constructed and validated by the investigator to assess the Emotional Intelligence Scale by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Dethe and Upinder Dhar (2001) has been adopted by the investigator for the present study. This tool consisted of 105 items under five alternatives such as strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree and strongly disagree which was modified and validated. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.67. This tool is also a five point scale which includes the with scoring 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively for positive items and 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 for negative items.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists in the mean scores of higher secondary student's emotional intelligence between male and female.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists in the mean scores of higher secondary student's emotional intelligence between rural and urban.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of type of management with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of religion with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of caste with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists in the mean scores of higher secondary student's emotional intelligence between government employed and self employed.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of higher secondary student's emotional intelligence between male and female.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of higher secondary student's emotional intelligence between rural and urban.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of caste with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their higher secondary student's emotional intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of parental occupation of emotional intelligence between government employed and self employed.

Analysis of Data:

Gender and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 1: 't' test between Mean Scores of Male and Female Higher Secondary Students towards Emotional Intelligence

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	133	109.62	35.01	0.747	NS
Female	107	112.90	32.33		

It is evident from the Table 1; the calculated 't' value is 0.747, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Locality of school and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 2: 't' test between Mean Scores of Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Students towards Emotional Intelligence

Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	107	112.41	33.65	0.543	NS
Urban	133	110.02	34.04		

It is evident from the Table 2; the calculated 't' value is 0.543, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Type of Management and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 3: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Type of Management with Respect To Their Emotional Intelligence

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	1884.236	942.118	2	0.823	NS
Within Groups	271466.927	1145.430	237		
Total	273351.162		239		

It is evident from the Table 3; the calculated 'F' value is 0.823, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.

Religion and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 4: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Religion with Respect To Their Emotional Intelligence

Religion	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	3107.845	1553.922	2	1.363	NS
Within Groups	270243.318	1140.267	237		
Total	273351.162		239		

It is evident from the Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 1.363, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.

Caste and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 5: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Caste with Respect To Their Emotional Intelligence

Caste	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	1585.925	528.642	3	0.459	NS
Within Groups	271765.238	1151.548	236		
Total	273351.163		239		

It is evident from the Table 5, the calculated 'F' value is 0.459, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of caste with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.

Parental Qualification and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 6: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Parental Qualification with Respect To Their Emotional Intelligence

Parental Qualification	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	1493.736	746.868	2	0.651	NS
Within Groups	271857.426	1147.078	237		
Total	273351.163		239		

It is evident from the Table 6, the calculated 'F' value is 0.651, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.

Parental occupation and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 7: 't' test between Mean Scores of Parental Occupation towards Emotional Intelligence

Parental Occupation	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Govt employ	104	112.24	32.71	0.461	NS
Self employ	136	110.20	34.73		

It is evident from the Table 7; the calculated 't' value is 0.461, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between govt employ and self employ of parental occupation with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of caste with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between govt employ and self employ of parental occupation with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Educational Implications:

- ✓ Awareness programme should be conducted to the teachers about different dimensions of emotional intelligence.
- ✓ Innovative modern teaching strategies should be incorporated to develop interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence.
- ✓ Training must be given to teachers regarding language laboratory, digital library, e-library and CAI in order to develop verbal linguistic intelligence among the teachers.
- ✓ Teaching strategies should be developed by using different dimensions of intelligence.
- ✓ Workshops and seminars may be conducted for teachers.
- ✓ In-service training must be given to the teachers to develop their multiple intelligence.
- ✓ Democratic approach in administration will enable teachers to be competent in new areas.

Recommendations for the Present Study:

- ✓ Skill based workshops, conferences and seminars must be organized periodically to develop these skills in these areas.
- ✓ Psychological skill based activities to be promoted in teacher education institutions to promote among the teachers.
- ✓ Quality of the programme has to be still more improved to develop the emotional intelligence to teachers.

Delimitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is confined to measure the emotional intelligence only.
- ✓ This study has been restricted only to the higher secondary teachers in Government, government, aided and private,
- ✓ This study is carried out taking 240 higher secondary students as sample.

Conclusion:

Ones intelligence is an innate as well as acquired intellectual potential. Every child is born with some intellectual potential which grows and develops with the help of maturity and experiences. Similarly, one is also born with some innate emotional intelligence in terms of one's level of emotional sensitivity, emotional memory, emotional processing and emotional learning ability. This potential (unlike intelligence) is liable to be developed or damaged as a result of one's experiences. The difference here is between the development pattern of innate emotional intelligence and general intelligence as a result of maturity of experiences.

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